

Philosophy

To me, teaching and mentoring are among the most fulfilling aspects of an academic position and I am motivated to help students grow to meet future challenges. In addition to informal teaching through peer groups (including work with the SIO/UCSD R Users Group that led to being a co-recipient of the E. W. Fager Memorial Award in 2014), I have sought out formal training and opportunities in pedagogy (a 9-week course in evidence based teaching at the UCSD Teaching + Learning Commons; and the 2-day Carpentries Instructor Training workshop) and leadership (I completed Mozilla's Open Leadership Training Series, am co-founder of the SIO/UCSD R Users Group, and served as board member of the UF Carpentries Club). Out of this training and experience, I focus on three general principles in my approach to teaching:

1. **Create a safe, inclusive, and accessible environment.**

If students worry about personal safety or classroom culture, then they are distracted from learning. Recognizing that students may have concerns, and addressing those concerns in a positive and proactive manner enables better learning. For example, I have helped create codes of conduct for both my lab and the UF Carpentries Club (<https://www.uf-carpentries.org/code-of-conduct/>) in order to set clear expectations on behavior.

2. **Explicitly define learning outcomes and expectations for the course.**

When I teach, I begin with a short summary of the goals for the lesson or workshop. This creates a conceptual scaffolding that helps students frame the lesson material in terms of how they may apply the knowledge, providing additional motivation. Within a larger structure, such as the syllabus for a course, the learning outcomes also guide me in deciding what exercises or content should be prioritized for inclusion.

3. **Use formative assessments to provide frequent and constructive feedback.**

Because lesson content is often cumulative, students who fall behind early can struggle to catch up. Formative assessments enable me to both adjust my pace as well as identify the conceptual errors that may need to be addressed on an individual- or class-level. For example, in Software/Data Carpentry computational workshops, students use different-colored sticky notes to indicate their status. Together with coding exercises, this practice ensures that students are ready to proceed to the next lesson, and enables students to request help without feeling like they are disrupting the class.

Proposed Courses

One possible course that I would be interested in teaching at the upper undergraduate or introductory graduate level focuses on data analysis in the context of a research or analysis project. Although students receive substantial training in biology, ecology, and statistics, they may not be familiar in combining this knowledge to enact a research project, from conceptualizing a specific question to choosing an appropriate statistical analysis, to presenting and communicating results. In my experience assisting other researchers with data analysis, reviewing papers, and handling manuscripts as an editor, one common area for improvement is in communicating how a research question is addressed through the statistical analysis. Thus, I believe training in bringing together tools and knowledge will be a highly valuable experience for students. In addition, in any analysis, there are numerous workflow aspects (e.g. organizing

raw and processed data files) that are critical for success, but often not explicitly taught (because experienced practitioners view these skills as mundane or trivial). Providing explicit instruction on these steps of a data analytic workflow (e.g. data cleaning, statistical analysis, communicating and visualizing results), will ensure that students are equipped to handle future challenges.

My learning objectives are for students to acquire the ability to process and analyze data on a computer, and to generalize beyond the skills learned in class and identify new tools, statistical methods, software, etc. as needed for their future projects. Materials for this class would be adapted from existing open educational resources, such as <https://datacarpentry.org/semester-biology/> and <https://sites.trinity.edu/osl/>. In turn, I would publish my course content as an open educational resource for others to adopt, adapt, or contribute to. The class would conclude with a self-guided project, giving students the opportunity to combine all of the individual skills, and for instruction in giving and receiving peer feedback.

Among graduate courses, my most valuable experiences have focused on practical skills that I continue to use today. For that reason, some possible graduate seminars include:

1. **Evaluate scientific outputs and give constructive feedback.**

Although students know what scientific papers are, they are often unfamiliar with the steps involved in publication. To address this gap, I will adopt and extend the PRereview (<https://v2.prereview.org/>) model, with students working in groups to develop critical and constructive peer-reviews. This would be accompanied with discussions of authorship and the editorial process. Students will thus gain practical experience in formal peer-review, while also producing useful feedback for preprint authors. The reviews will additionally be minted with DOIs, so that students receive academic credit, and enabling their findability as potential reviewers (a common challenge for early career researchers).

2. **Learn best practices in data analysis and reproduce published results.**

Analyzing research data can be hugely intimidating—there are numerous decisions to make, statistical results to interpret, and it is often unclear whether the intended calculations were done correctly! To help students gain practical experience in reproducible research, I will structure a course around reproducing published results and interweave training from "Good Enough Practices in Scientific Computing" (Wilson et al. 2017). This would follow previous examples, such as Owen Petchey's RREEBES course (<https://github.com/opetchey/RREEBES>), Anna Krystalli's ReproHack event (https://github.com/annakrystalli/OpenConBerlin_ReproHack), Timothée Poisot's "Biological modelling and simulations" course at the University of Montréal. Finally, the reproductions will be submitted to an online repository, The ReScience Journal (<https://github.com/ReScience/ReScience>), to document the students' work.

Summary

The above descriptions are just some of the courses that I would be interested in teaching. I sympathize with the fact that many students are unlikely to be professional academics, and can benefit from career advice from outside the university. At UF, I address this issue by creating career panels (e.g. <https://resbaz.github.io/resbaz2019/gainesville/#schedule>) that include representatives from local tech companies, government agencies, the university innovation office, etc. to speak about transferable skills and finding suitable careers.